

Milestone: M3.6.2 Final release of the Accessible Genome Dashboard

Lead Participant: VUmc

Author: Jeroen Belien

Due: 30 June 2023

Date Of Completion: 30 June 2023

Means of Verification

<https://dashboard.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

All open issues (e.g. deduplication of FinnGen dataset have been taken care off)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

Collaborative work:

Task lead: Jeroen Belien (VUmc)

Dashboard based on [1+MG survey](#) (all 1+MG WGs, coordinated by Astrid Vicente & Szymon Bielecki)

ELIXIR-hub: Juan Arenas

Sub-contracting VUmc & Health-RI: (portal development) Wouter van Stralen and Jesper Peterse

Next action steps

More information on survey can be released on dashboard but only after data holders have been reconsented. Might be a tile on the GDI user portal (pending reconsenting).

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